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IMPROVING TAX ADMINISTRATION IN UZBEKISTAN AND ITS SOLUTIONS

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasida soliq ma'murchiligi tizimini takomillashtirish va transformatsiya qilishning strategik yo'nalishlari tadqiq etilgan. Tadqiqot davomida soliq to'lovchilarga xizmat ko'rsatish sifatini yanada oshirish, yashirin iqtisodiyot ulushini bosqichma-bosqich qisqartirish hamda raqamli texnologiyalarni samarali joriy etish masalalari tahlil qilingan. Maqolada soliq nazorati jarayonlarini avtomatlashtirish, inson omilini kamaytirish va soliq ma'murchiligi samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha mualliflik takliflari hamda ilmiy asoslangan yechimlar ilgari surilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: soliq ma'murchiligi, strategik rivojlanish, raqamlashtirish, yashirin iqtisodiyot, soliq nazorati, xavflarni tahlil qilish, soliq islohotlari.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются стратегические направления совершенствования и трансформации системы налогового администрирования в Республике Узбекистан. В ходе исследования проанализированы вопросы дальнейшего повышения качества обслуживания налогоплательщиков, поэтапного сокращения доли теневой экономики и эффективного внедрения цифровых технологий. В статье представлены авторские предложения и научно обоснованные решения, направленные на автоматизацию процессов налогового контроля, снижение влияния человеческого фактора и повышение эффективности налогового администрирования.

Ключевые слова: налоговое администрирование, стратегическое развитие, цифровизация, теневая экономика, налоговый контроль, анализ рисков, налоговые реформы.

Abstract. This article examines the strategic directions for improving and transforming the tax administration system in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The study analyzes issues related to further improving the quality of taxpayer services, gradually reducing the share of the shadow economy, and effectively introducing digital technologies. The article presents the author's proposals and scientifically grounded solutions aimed at automating tax control processes, reducing the influence of the human factor, and enhancing the efficiency of tax administration.

Keywords: tax administration, strategic development, digitalization, shadow economy, tax control, risk analysis, tax reforms.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of a modern market economy, ensuring the stability of state budget revenues and further improving the business environment are directly related to the efficiency of the tax system. Within the framework of the objectives defined in the New Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, reducing the tax burden and simplifying tax administration are considered among the priority areas. At present, reorganizing the activities of tax authorities based on the principle of "tax officer — assistant," improving the legal culture of taxpayers, and fully digitalizing the tax system are becoming increasingly important. At the same time, the need to reduce the share of the shadow economy, minimize the influence of the human factor in tax control, and improve the efficiency of information exchange requires the strategic improvement of this sector. The purpose of this article is to scientifically analyze the existing issues in Uzbekistan's tax system and develop scientific and practical proposals aimed at improving the efficiency of tax administration based on international experience.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Western economists S. Fischer, R. Dornbusch, and R. Schmalensee [1], tax policy is not considered an independent concept but is interpreted as part of fiscal policy. According to their approach, fiscal policy refers to the process by which the state makes decisions regarding its revenues and expenditures.

A. V. Aronov and V. A. Kashin [2] interpret the concept of maximum tax policy as one of the main strategies of tax policy. In their view, increasing the number of taxes, raising tax rates, and reducing tax benefits may be considered strategic directions of tax policy.

I. A. Mayburov [3] defines tax reform as a process of fundamentally changing the tax system and adapting it to the new content of state tax policy.

N. M. Dementyeva [4] considers tax policy to be an important reflection of state economic policy. In her

opinion, tax policy has independent significance and should be based on the scientific theory of taxation. She also emphasizes that the results of implemented tax policy determine what adjustments should be made to state economic policy and how the tax system should be formed.

M. V. Karp [5] interprets tax policy as an integral part of the state's medium- and long-term general financial policy. He emphasizes that tax policy includes such concepts as the concept of state activity in the field of taxation, the tax mechanism, and the management of the tax system.

According to O. Sitnikova [6], when including entities in a consolidated group of taxpayers, it is necessary to recognize assets or carry out their special revaluation. In addition, attention should be paid to developing a procedure for transferring enterprise losses before joining the group and to the international recognition of the consolidated taxpayer as a single entity with financial and economic activity.

Yu. Darkina [7], focusing on the characteristics of large taxpayers, notes that they are characterized by large cash flows, extensive document circulation, the integration of various structural divisions, and cooperation with different firms both within the country and abroad.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study used analytical, comparative, and systematic research methods. The analytical method was applied to examine the current state of tax administration in Uzbekistan, including digitalization, tax control, taxpayer services, and risk management.

The comparative method was used to study international practices, particularly OECD standards, BEPS requirements, Compliance Risk Management, and approaches to reducing the tax gap. The systematic method helped assess the relationship between tax administration reforms, digital technologies, the reduction of the human factor, and the expansion of the tax base.

The research was based on scientific literature, strategic documents, official data of the Tax Committee, and materials related to the 2026–2030 Tax Administration Development Strategy. As a result, practical recommendations were developed to improve transparency, efficiency, and digital transformation in Uzbekistan's tax administration system.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The Strategy for the Development of Tax Administration and Tax Authorities for 2026–2030 was developed in accordance with the "Uzbekistan – 2030" Strategy. This document aims to bring the activities of tax authorities to a qualitatively new stage, consistently continue the digitalization of tax services, simplify reporting procedures, ensure transparency in tax administration, and improve the efficiency of human resource utilization.

Existing Opportunities and Areas for Improvement in the System

In order to use the available resources in the tax system more rationally and improve the quality of services provided to business entities, it is important to improve the following areas:

First, it is necessary to further align the services provided to taxpayers with international standards, develop a unified service delivery model, and expand the system of free tax consultations;

Second, it is important to reduce the share of the shadow economy and further strengthen a healthy competitive environment by preventing cases of income concealment and tax evasion;

Third, it is advisable to introduce the National Audit Plan and the Compliance Improvement Plan in order to expand opportunities for identifying and effectively eliminating systemic tax risks;

Fourth, in the context of a high level of digitalization, it is necessary to make effective use of external data sources, identify additional tax bases, and further strengthen analytical processes;

Fifth, it is important to formulate a unified policy for developing human resource capacity, introduce modern management methods, and ensure the stability of qualified personnel in regional tax authorities.

Goals and Objectives of the Strategy

The main goal of the strategy is to ensure that, by 2030, Uzbekistan ranks among the top 50 countries in the world in terms of the convenience of tax policy and tax administration in international rankings. To achieve this goal, the following priority tasks have been identified:

- to ensure stable tax revenues and bring tax service delivery to a new level;
- to introduce innovative approaches in the tax advisory system and expand the tax base by improving tax culture;
- to create additional sources of budget revenue, prevent cases of tax evasion, and create favorable conditions for entrepreneurs to fulfill their tax obligations;
- to strengthen analytical analysis through the use of Big Data technologies, artificial intelligence, and automated systems;

- to introduce a modern human resource management system, identify and assess operational risks, and implement a strategy for minimizing them.

Priority Areas and Implementation Mechanisms of the Strategy

The priority areas of the strategy are aimed at further digitalizing the tax system, providing convenient and prompt services to taxpayers, reducing the share of the shadow economy, increasing analytical capacity, and developing human capital within tax authorities. Effective implementation of these areas will further improve the transparency, efficiency, and quality of service delivery in tax administration.

Implementation Measures under the Tax Administration and Tax Authorities Development Strategy for 2026–2030

To ensure the effective implementation of the objectives set out in the Strategy for the Development of Tax Administration and Tax Authorities for 2026–2030, a series of measures will be undertaken across the following strategic priority areas.

Service-Oriented Approach and Transparency

Within the framework of introducing a qualitatively new model of taxpayer services, the following initiatives are envisaged:

- Establishing a unified taxpayer support system to ensure the prompt handling of taxpayer inquiries and to implement the principle that “no inquiry remains unanswered”;
- Conducting independent public surveys to assess the level of trust in tax authorities and regularly publishing the results;
- Publishing comprehensive quarterly reports on tax administration performance, analytical findings, and potential risk factors on the official website;
- Simplifying the process of refunding overpaid taxes through the effective utilization of the Unified Treasury Account system and ensuring the stability and predictability of tax reporting procedures;

Developing a unified electronic database containing information on the income of high-net-worth individuals.

Tax Risk Management (CRM) and the Promotion of a Fair Competitive Environment

To strengthen tax compliance and enhance the effectiveness of the Compliance Risk Management (CRM) framework, the following measures will be implemented:

- Preparing annual National Audit Plans and Compliance Improvement Plans (CIPs) aimed at identifying and mitigating tax risks across economic sectors;
 - Automating the identification and registration of informally operating entities through enhanced interagency information exchange mechanisms;
 - Upgrading CRM modules capable of forecasting taxpayer behavior and improving algorithms used for selecting audit candidates;
 - Enhancing the methodology for assessing the sustainability ratings of business entities and improving the effectiveness of desk-based tax audits;
 - Optimizing mechanisms for the recovery of tax arrears from taxpayers’ treasury and special-purpose accounts, as well as improving procedures related to asset restrictions where necessary;
- Regularly publishing practical guidance materials on tax compliance issues to assist taxpayers in preventing errors and improving voluntary compliance.

Analysis of Key Areas for Improvement within the Tax System

The ongoing modernization of Uzbekistan’s tax system is focused on maximizing the efficient use of available resources and elevating service delivery to a new level. In this regard, particular attention is being devoted to the development of a unified taxpayer service model, the alignment of free tax advisory services with international best practices, and the strengthening of a fair competitive environment through the reduction of tax evasion and income concealment practices.

Furthermore, the introduction of the National Audit Plan and the Compliance Improvement Plan is expected to significantly enhance the effectiveness of tax control activities. Expanding digitalization initiatives will create additional opportunities to utilize external data sources, apply Big Data analytics to identify additional tax bases, and strengthen analytical capabilities. At the same time, improving human resource development policies and introducing modern HR management practices will contribute to increasing the institutional effectiveness and sustainability of tax authorities.

Strategic Development Priorities for 2026–2030

1. Service-Oriented Approach and Transparency

To strengthen transparency within tax authorities and further institutionalize the principle of “Tax Officer as a Facilitator,” the following measures will be undertaken:

- Establishment of a centralized system for the prompt processing of taxpayer inquiries;
- Provision of mechanisms enabling taxpayers to independently manage and update their activity status;
- Further simplification of tax refund procedures through the enhancement of the Unified Treasury Account

mechanism;

Creation of a unified electronic database covering income information of high-income individuals.

2. Compliance Risk Management

To foster a fair competitive environment and strengthen tax discipline, the following priority measures will be implemented:

- Development of comprehensive sector-specific mechanisms for assessing and mitigating tax risks;
- Further improvement of automated risk assessment modules and CRM systems designed to predict taxpayer behavior;
- Strengthening tax debt recovery mechanisms through the application of advanced digital technologies and information systems;

Implementation of specialized monitoring algorithms aimed at preventing tax evasion in the construction sector.

Overall, the strategic priorities outlined for 2026–2030 are expected to transform tax administration into a more transparent, efficient, and service-oriented system. Moreover, the extensive application of digital technologies, advanced analytical tools, and human capital development initiatives will further strengthen the institutional capacity and long-term effectiveness of the tax authorities.

3. Digitalization and Innovation

Within the framework of improving technological efficiency, the following measures will be implemented:

- direct electronic integration with data from ministries, agencies, and commercial banks will be ensured;
- “Big Data”, artificial intelligence (AI), and machine learning technologies will be widely introduced into analytical processes;
- digital mechanisms for taxing e-commerce and service sectors will be further optimized.

In terms of human resource capacity development, an “HR Capacity Development” program based on the principle of meritocracy will be implemented in tax authorities. In addition, a systematic approach to identifying, assessing, and managing operational risks within the system will be introduced.

Strategic Target Indicators by 2030

As a result of the implementation of the defined tasks, the following indicators are planned to be achieved:

- increasing the share of tax revenues in GDP from 20 percent to 23 percent;
- raising the voluntary tax compliance rate to 97 percent;
- increasing the share of active individual taxpayers to 99 percent;

ranking among the top 50 countries in the world in terms of the convenience of tax administration in international rankings.

Practical Mechanisms for the Strategic Transformation of Tax Administration

The strategic transformation of tax administration will be carried out through the following practical mechanisms.

Service-Oriented Approach and Transparency

In order to bring cooperation with taxpayers to a new level, a separate centralized service delivery structure will be established. Within this framework, the AI-based “Davron” assistant for tax advisory services will be further improved, and the principle that “no question should remain unanswered” will be introduced.

Surveys assessing public trust in tax authorities will be conducted with the participation of independent organizations, and their results will be published in the mass media. The Public Council under the Tax Committee will become an important consultative platform for discussing draft regulatory legal acts.

Taxpayers will be given the opportunity to independently change their activity status electronically through their personal accounts. It will also be legally established that amendments to tax reporting forms may be introduced only once a year and at least 60 days before the beginning of the new reporting period.

Tax Risk Management and Control Efficiency

A number of important measures will be implemented to qualitatively improve the tax compliance system. In particular, it is planned to increase the number of highly qualified employees conducting tax audits to 2,000 by 2030 and to develop a National Audit Plan.

All processes, including requests for documents and the submission of audit results, will be carried out through the taxpayer’s transparent personal account. The role of the human factor in maintaining the business sustainability rating will be gradually reduced.

In order to reduce the risk of legal violations, clear criteria will be applied to the procedure for refunding VAT without inspections for certain categories of enterprises. Mechanisms for collecting tax debts from taxpayers’ treasury and special accounts, as well as procedures for imposing restrictions on property, will be improved within the legal framework.

3. Expansion of Taxable Objects and Incentive Mechanisms

New mechanisms will be introduced to reduce the shadow economy and increase budget revenues.

Regarding personal income declarations, a system of mandatory declaration of income and expenses by civil servants and high-income individuals will be introduced gradually.

To encourage early payments, a 5 percent discount will be provided to those who pay property and land taxes by March 1, while a 3 percent discount will be applied to payments made by July 1.

Based on the "Shofirkon experience", the mechanism for calculating taxes for individuals transporting subsoil minerals without registration through surveillance camera monitoring will be expanded.

The practice of determining the tax base for real estate based on its market value will be further improved. This will contribute to increasing the fairness and economic justification of the taxation system.

4. Innovative Analysis and International Methodology

Modern analytical programs and international methodologies will be applied to reduce the tax gap. In particular, through the RA-Gap program, tax avoidance methods will be analyzed using both "top-down" and "bottom-up" approaches.

Separate Compliance Improvement Plans will be developed for sectors such as construction, transport, retail trade, and rental services. This will make it possible to accurately assess tax risks in each sector and determine appropriate management measures.

Digitalization, Transparency, and International Standards

In recent years, reforming tax administration has become one of the priority areas in the modernization of Uzbekistan's economy. In accordance with the newly approved action plan, significant technological, organizational, and legal changes will be implemented in the tax system.

These reforms will contribute to increasing the transparency of the tax system, creating convenience for taxpayers, reducing the share of the shadow economy, and ensuring the stability of state budget revenues. At the same time, digital technologies, artificial intelligence, and analytical approaches based on international standards will further strengthen the efficiency of tax administration.

1. "Smart" Algorithms in Audit and Control

From now on, the selection of candidates for tax audits will be carried out without human involvement, based entirely on automated algorithms. The system for identifying discrepancies and errors in taxpayers' data will be improved, and new modules aimed at optimizing audit processes will be launched. This will help reduce unnecessary inspections for honest entrepreneurs and ensure that tax control is organized in a fair and efficient manner.

2. Data Integrity and Interagency Integration

In order to ensure the accuracy of the taxpayer register, continuous data exchange will be established among the Tax Committee, the Statistics Agency, and the Ministry of Justice. The number of legal entities and individuals will be continuously monitored. The IBM Cognos Analytics system will be introduced in tax authorities to work with large volumes of data, namely Big Data. This system will expand forecasting opportunities by separating data into transactional and analytical components.

3. International Standards and OECD Requirements

In order to integrate Uzbekistan's tax system into the international environment, important amendments will be made to the Tax Code, and international mechanisms will be gradually implemented. In particular, mechanisms for the automatic and on-request exchange of tax information, the prevention of tax base erosion, and the transfer of profits abroad will be improved. In addition, the introduction of a three-tier documentation system based on international standards is envisaged.

4. Financial Transaction Control and Transparency

One of the important areas of the new reforms is the monitoring of suspicious transactions on bank plastic cards. If more than 100 transfers are made to one individual's card within one month, or if the total amount exceeds 200 times the base calculation amount, this information will be automatically transferred to the tax authorities. In addition, integration with commercial banks will be strengthened, and the mechanism for obtaining information on the turnover of legal entities' and individuals' bank accounts will be simplified. This will contribute to increasing financial transparency and forming the tax base more accurately.

5. Cybersecurity and Human Resource Capacity

The digitalization of the tax system further increases the need to ensure data security. Therefore, regular training sessions on cybersecurity and encryption methods will be organized for employees of the Tax Committee. This will serve to reliably protect taxpayers' personal and financial data, strengthen information security, and increase trust in the system.

6. Tax Monitoring: Transition from Control to Cooperation

One of the key innovations in the tax system is the introduction of a remote tax monitoring system. Technical measures will be taken to enable large taxpayers to provide tax authorities with access to their accounting reports. Desk audits and tax audits will not be conducted for enterprises that voluntarily join the program. In addition, the practice of tax authorities preparing tax reports for taxpayers will be introduced. This approach will

take cooperation between taxpayers and tax authorities to a new level.

7. Regulation of the Digital Economy and E-Commerce

The development of digital technologies requires modern methods for identifying the tax base. In this regard, mechanisms for taxing e-commerce and service sectors will be improved. Special attention will be paid to expanding the tax base through the analysis of postal and international courier shipments. This approach will increase the adaptability of tax administration in the digital economy.

8. Database Optimization — OLTP and OLAP

Within the framework of database optimization, OLTP systems will be used for the rapid processing of daily transactions, while OLAP systems will be applied for preparing complex analytical data and conducting an in-depth analysis of the tax base. This separation will make it possible to increase system performance several times, conduct accurate analyses based on large volumes of data, and improve the quality of forecasting.

9. Infrastructure Modernization and Improvement of Staff Qualifications

In order to fully digitalize tax administration, the material and technical base will be modernized step by step. Master classes will be organized for IT specialists, and the advanced experience of foreign countries in digital tax administration will be studied and introduced into practice.

In addition, all functions and services of tax authorities that have not yet been digitalized will be inventoried. After that, work will be carried out on the basis of a strict roadmap to gradually transfer them into electronic form. This will be an important step toward reducing the human factor, preventing corruption risks, and further improving the efficiency of the tax system.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The planned reforms in Uzbekistan's tax system are aimed at fundamentally transforming tax administration. In this process, the main focus is placed on reducing the human factor, fully digitalizing tax services, increasing transparency, and creating a more convenient environment for taxpayers.

Tax audit and monitoring will gradually move away from subjective approaches and rely on Big Data analysis and automated algorithms. This will help reduce the administrative burden on honest taxpayers, improve the effectiveness of inspections, and ensure that tax control is organized fairly.

The introduction of OECD standards and BEPS requirements will increase the transparency of the national economy and strengthen Uzbekistan's investment attractiveness in the international arena. In addition, the separation of databases into OLTP and OLAP systems, together with the strengthening of cybersecurity measures, will raise the analytical capacity of tax authorities to a new level.

Remote monitoring of e-commerce and banking transactions will serve as an important factor in reducing the share of the shadow economy, expanding the tax base, and ensuring the stability of budget revenues.

In conclusion, the comprehensive implementation of these measures will not only ensure the stability of state budget revenues but also contribute to the formation of a convenient, fair, and digital tax environment for taxpayers.

The study of foreign experience shows the need to develop a multi-component approach to assessing the effectiveness of tax policy. Based on this, it is advisable to put forward the following recommendations:

- to take into account non-taxable or preferential turnover, taxable objects, specific groups of taxpayers, and sectoral characteristics when assessing the real level of the tax burden on the economy;
- to ensure the guaranteed fulfillment of forecast indicators for tax revenues in the revenue part of the state budget in order to provide stable financing for state activities;
- to reduce tax risks and widely use modern digital analytical tools in their management;
- to ensure the harmony of the resource-based approach and the target-oriented approach in the implementation of tax policy in order to achieve the defined strategic goals;
- to gradually introduce international experience, digital technologies, and innovative management mechanisms into national practice in the process of improving tax administration.

The practical implementation of the above recommendations will contribute to the further improvement of tax administration in Uzbekistan, the deepening of digitalization processes, and the enhancement of the overall efficiency of the tax system.

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